

Instructional Leadership Skills of the Public Secondary School Administrators of Malasiqui District II-A

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Abstract

This study investigated the instructional leadership skills of public secondary school administrators in Malasiqui District II-A, Pangasinan during the 2025-2026 school year. Using a descriptive-normative survey method with 30 school managers and 135 teachers as respondents, the study examined leadership skills across four dimensions: provider, instructional resources leader, communicator, and visible presence. Findings revealed that school managers demonstrated very satisfactory skills as providers (AWM=3.51) and in visible presence (AWM=3.56), while skills as instructional resources leader (AWM=3.16) and communicator (AWM=3.39) required improvement. Teachers perceived provider skills as very satisfactory (AWM=3.56) but rated other dimensions as fairly satisfactory. Serious problems affecting instructional leadership included overlapping activities (AWM=3.20) and limited funding (AWM=2.87). No significant differences existed between 管理者 and teacher perceptions across most dimensions. An action plan was developed to enhance instructional leadership competencies.

Keywords: *instructional leadership skills, school administrators, provider role, instructional resources, communicator skills, visible presence, secondary education, educational management, Pangasinan, action plan*

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM

Rationale

The aspiration and dreams of our people as well as our country facing the twenty first century is to achieve the expected quality education for all that would bring socio-economic, moral and cultural upliftment of all Filipinos. This dream and aspirations for quality instruction depend greatly on the instructional leadership of the school managers like principals and heads of the secondary school which is the focus of this research.

Since we are people destined to live in a fast changing world, education through instructional leadership of the school managers should lead to the avenue of social, cultural managers should lead to the avenue of social, cultural, personal and moral development of the subjects. It is imperative that teachers and principals should achieve the desired learning outcomes not only because they are empowered, competent and accountable, but because they are: where administrators ensure adequate resources and promote the use of appropriate technology to enhance learning and where the family, the community, private schools and other institutions extend their support to achieve the vision of the Department of Education, Culture and Sports which is: To enable the Filipino child to discover his/her full potential in a child – centered and value – driven teaching – learning environment. Thereby, he/she will create his/her own destiny in a global community. Prepare him/her to become responsible citizen and enlightenment leader who loves his/her country and is proud to be a Filipino. However, speaking of leadership skills it is inevitable to say that it involves creativity process. The measure of leaderships is not the quality of the head, or school managers but the atmosphere of the group or institution. The signs of understanding leadership appear primarily among the followers or subordinates. Are the followers reaching their potentials? Are they learning? Serving? Do they believe and achieve the required-results? Do they change with grace? Manage conflict?

To have leaderships are and develop skills thereto involves self-denial and sacrifice of time that induces the leaders or the school managers to be concerned with the institutional value system which after all leads to the principles and standards that guide the practice of the people in the institutions, to be responsible for such thing as a sense of quality in the institution for whether or not the institution is open to influence and open to change, to have a sense of self-worth, a sense of expectancy, a sense of responsibility, a sense of accountability, and a sense of quality.

On the side of educational leadership, it is a delicate and worthy task to aspire then to the idea of quality, standard and effectiveness of instruction, it is not only the task of the school leaders or managers particularly in the secondary levels to elicit and encourage participation in the activities prepared to be accomplished. They must know how to delegate efficiency and deal personally with effectiveness, understanding that effectiveness comes about through enabling others to reach their potentials both their personal potential and their institutional potential.

The school managers in the secondary level then to conclude must take a role and lead in developing, expressing and defending civility and values, since in a civilized institution like ours we see good manners, respect for persons, and an appreciation of the way in which we sense each other. It is to make a meaningful difference in the lives of those who permit leaders to lead, and that instructional leaderships skills are geared toward improvement of qualitative education

not only in the secondary level of education but to all other levels per se.

Conceptual Framework

The greatest question in the view point of education particularly on teaching learning scenario is; how can instruction in both elementary and much so in the secondary be meaningful and effective? Well, the answers to the questions lies on the leaderships capability of any head or any manager of the schools particularly in the secondary level. To lead the teachers and other people concerned under them needs some sort of creative imagination, art and skills to accomplish the goals set for instruction. It is the leaderships of the secondary school managers to be definite to look into the essence of instruction. In so doing they would be able to uplift the standard of education in the Philippines and that they young minds under their care would become effective builders of our country in the future.

It is necessary that the secondary school managers of the Urbiztondo, Division of Pangasinan I possess the qualities and strengths of being able to communicate effectively in both oral and written, being to provide the teachers the related tasks for instruction, being a resourceful leader and radiate as well as actualize their presence to push and motivate the teachers to work as a school team. School managers so to speak are coordinators, orientors, consultants, researchers, public relation person, change agents and stimulators. These are the multiple personalities of school managers who are equipped of instructional leadership skills.

A rational look on the issue, the researcher believe that the primarily task of a school manager is to manage learning and instruction which is referred to planning, organizing, directing, motivating, controlling and evaluating the objectives of instruction.

Instructional leaderships then is a quality that demands knowledgeability focused action and shared determination on the improvement of insurrection. It requires the conceptualization, implementation and evaluation of activities, projects intended to realize instructional goals and provides the links between the implementors and the object of instructional program of the unit.

These above mentioned personally profile, educational profile, leaderships skills and managerial competence of the secondary school managers will bring to the best solution and answer to the personal problems on instruction.

Operational Paradigm of the Study

This figure one presents the operational paradigm of the study on “Instructional Leadership Skills of the Public Secondary Schools Managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan during the school year 2025 – 2026”.

This independent variables of the study are: profile of the public secondary school manager as regard to: personal profile, professional profile composed of educational qualification, year of experience, scholarship, seminar training, and reading materials; instructional leadership skills manifested by the public secondary school managers of the first congressional district of Pangasinan perform their role to enhance leadership skills; and problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the public secondary school managers of the first congressional district of Pangasinan and the action plan.

The dependent variables are: information of the profile of the public school managers of the first congressional district of Pangasinan as regard to; personal profile, professional profile like; educational qualifications, years of experience, seminar training, and reading materials; extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the public secondary school

manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan as: provider, instructional resources leader, and visible presence; and the comparison between the perception of the school managers and teachers on the extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the secondary school manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan; the degree of extent to which the public secondary school manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan perform their roles to enhance leadership skills, and the comparison between the perception of the school managers and teachers of the public secondary school of the first congressional district on the degree of extent to which they perform their roles to enhance leadership skills; and the degree of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the public secondary school manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan and the comparison between the perception of the school manager and teachers of the public secondary schools of the first congressional district of Pangasinan on the degree of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the public secondary school managers and the degree of implementing the action plan.

The expected outcomes are: to upgrade the manager's profile along professional aspects; improve the instructional leadership skills of the public secondary school manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan as provider, instructional resources leader, communicator and visible presence; better performance of the roles of the public secondary school manager of the first congressional district of Pangasinan to enhance leadership skills; and solutions to the problems that affect instructional leadership performance of the public secondary school managers of the first congressional district of Pangasinan and the strict implementation of the action plan.

Operational Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This research deals on the “Instructional Leadership Skills of the Secondary School Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I for the school year 2025 – 2026”.

Specifically, it answers the following related questions:

1. What is the profile of the public secondary school Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I as regard to their:
 - a. personal profile
 - b. professional profile
 - b.1. educational qualification
 - b.2. years experience
 - b.3. scholarship
 - b.4. seminar training
 - b.5. reading materials
2. What is the extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the secondary school Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I as:
 - a. provider
 - b. instructional resources leader
 - c. communicator
 - d. visible presence
- 2.a. Is there any significant difference between the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the school administrators?
3. What is the extent to which the school administrators perform their roles to enhance leadership skills?
 - 3.a Is there any significant difference between the perception of the public secondary school administrators and teachers as to the extent to which the school administrators perform their roles to enhance leadership skill?
4. What is the degree of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the public secondary school Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of

Pangasinan I?

5. What action plan to be evolved to improve the status-skills of secondary school administrators?

Null Hypotheses

It is imperative that in this research the following null hypotheses will be statistically tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the school administrators and teachers in the extent of the school administrators and teachers in the extent to which the instructional leadership skills will be manifested by the school managers of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan as:
 - a. provider
 - b. instructional resources leader
 - c. communicator
 - d. visible presence
2. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the school administrators and the teachers as to the extent to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills.
3. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the school managers and teachers in the degree of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the secondary school administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The researcher in his aspiration to elucidate his study, he delimited it to Instructional Leadership Skills of the Public Secondary School Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I. It covers the areas on the profile of the secondary school Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I as in personal profile, and professional profile; extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the secondary school administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 as: provider, instructional resources leader, communicator, and visible presence; extent to which the school administrators perform their roles to enhance leadership skills; and the degree of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leaders performance of the secondary school administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I.

Definition of Terms

Instructional Leadership Skills. Refers to the abilities, strengths and personalities of the secondary school managers or any leader in any field of office that can build trust, or rapport, building, organizational diagnosis, resource diagnosis and building conference and skills in people to continue working for the accomplishment of the goals and objectives.

School managers. These are the school principals, heads of the different schools and officer-in-charge and heads therein who are responsible in leading, building, and managing instruction for better results of accomplishing the work.

Personal profile. Refers to the attributes of the respondents as to their sex, age, civil status, and origin of birth.

Professional profile. Refers to the educational qualifications of the school managers as

their designated positions, educational training and backgrounds, like courses or degrees obtained and years of experience related to their job.

Provider. It is one of the skills and attributes of any school manager that leads to the making of plans of activities, schedule of work and subjects, and prioritization of work to accomplished by the whole organization.

Instructional resources leader. Refers to the roles of the school managers to inform or share teachers of the latest research finding on teaching and learning share knowledge on teaching effectively, demonstrate ability to write curriculum, goals and objectives, and conduct conference, pre and post observations that include development objectives suggested by the staff members.

Communicator. This is the skills of the school manager that develops a system of open communication both written and oral, knows the appropriateness of communications which promotes mutual conflicts, resolution, problems solving, cooperation and sharing.

Visible presence. It is another skill of a school manager that express a clear vision for the school, organizes people, conduct needs assessment, involves self-actively, manage time to be out and around during school hours, check teachers daily teaching preparation and communicate clearly the responsibilities of teachers from student-learning.

Leadership. include followers to act towards goals that represents the value of both the leaders and followers to get the job done involving everyone in pursuing a share mission.

Supervision. It refers to all efforts of designated school managers directed toward improving leadership of teachers and other educational workers in the improvement of instruction.

Administration. This term includes all the techniques and procedures employed in operating the educational institution or organization in accordance with established policies.

Importance of the Study

It has been the dream and aspiration of the Philippine nation to live in the content of quality and excellence specially in the field of education. The Department of Education has been trying its best to live up to the expectation of the masses to work for quality teaching, quality learning through profound commitment in the aspect of instructional leadership skills of the school administrators like the principals, supervisor, superintendents, and heads of the different school all over the country.

This study would spell the difference between the quality instructional leadership skills of the secondary school Administrators of Malasiqui 1 and 2 Division of Pangasinan I and the excellent instructional leadership skills of the said administrators. It would challenge the school administrators all over the country if not internationally to make some sort of evaluation on the disposal of their instructional leadership skills so as to achieve the goals and objectives to secondary education which is on excellence and quality management and leadership as well as learning. It would all enhance the creativity process of the secondary school managers like the principal to become more aware of their duties and responsibilities as effective provider, instructional resources leader, communicator, and as visible presence to the school as family.

It would also be significant to the “would be administrators” to at least learn some ideas, concepts, and skills to become more effective and committed managers of their schools because the skills, leadership skills that the learned would help them solve their problems the encountered.

It would give avenues to both secondary administrators, teachers, elementary principals

and teachers to dispense their duties and responsibilities as leaders in their school and classrooms for the teachers since they would learn to become effective communicators and leaders with their visible presence.

This research would also be important for the other researchers who would embark on conducting similar research as this.

Related Literature

Smith describes a principal that displays strong instructional leadership as one who:

1. Places priority on curriculum and instruction issues.
2. Is dedicated to the goals of the school system.
3. Is able to rally and mobilize resources to accomplish the goals of the school.
4. Creates a climate of high expectations in the school, characterized by a tone of respect for teachers, students, parents, and community.
5. Functions as a leader with direct involvement in instruction policy by:
 - a. Communicating with teachers,
 - b. Supporting and participating in staff development activities,
 - c. Establishing teaching incentives for the use of instructional strategies,
 - d. Displaying knowledge for district / school adopted materials.
6. Continually monitors student progress toward school achievement and teacher effectiveness in meeting those goals. Teacher evaluation is:
 - a. characterized by frequent classroom visitation
 - b. is used to help students and teachers improve
7. Demonstrate commitment to academic goals, shown by the ability to develop and articulate a clear vision of long-term goals for the school, and to strong achievement goals and priorities.
8. Effectively consults with others by involving the faculty and other groups in school decision processes.
 - a. teachers feel they are genuinely encouraged to exchange ideas.
 - b. effectively functioning coalitions support the operation of the school, and the consistent groups share a commitment to the academic mission of the school
9. Effectively and efficiently mobilizes resources such as materials, time, and support to enable the school and its personnel to most effectively meet academic goals.
10. Recognizes time as a scarce resource and creates order and discipline by minimizing factors that may disrupt the learning process.

According to Andres, Filipino identifies leadership with benevolence because of the value of personalism. The focus is not so much on what a person does as who he is; not so much on what a person knows but whom he knows; not so much on the objective reality of things as actually received. He further stated that a leader must always be careful not to offend and of course to be offended. A must leader must be aware of the bargaining system of the Filipino before closing a commitment to attain certain objectives. He must also develop a sort of group of followers because of the Filipino value of "suki" system.

Tupas and Bernardo stated that leadership is not a monopoly of power. Rather, it is an interplay of stimulus and action every moving to reconceive goals in which everyone contributes his efforts as his talents and time permit. Furthermore, leadership is not exploitation and neither is it an abuse of trust. It is rather an expression of a covenant arising from consensus of the organization.

Roxas enumerated the various duties performed by principals, such as these:

1. Offering practical and constructive suggestions concerning the organizational procedure relative to the school wide program and the classroom through observation, demonstration and consultations.
2. Providing ample instructional and professional materials.

Organizational Techniques

1. The principals should develop a schedule which assures blocks of uninterrupted time for teaching. He should bring teachers into schedule-making by using their suggestions.
2. Insist that teachers plan classroom schedules conducive to wise use of time and help develop such schedules.
3. The principal should organize and plan his schedule so as to provide time for supervision work with teachers.
4. Know the teacher's classroom problems, works with them in solving these problems, and follow the progress they are making.
5. Do not delegate the job of classroom visitation to an assistant.

Consulting with Teachers

1. The principal should make himself available at regularly schedules time.
2. Study the strengths and weaknesses of individual teachers an build upon their strengths.
3. Schedule conferences and inform individuals and groups ahead of time, thereby allowing time to plan accordingly.
4. The principal should use conference time with young teachers to make practical lesson plans, and suggest specific classroom techniques and organizational procedures.
5. Encourage and participate in small group meetings on year levels, in subject areas, etc.
6. All faculty members should be given an opportunity to help plan group meetings by having them list areas of interest, serve on planning committees, and discuss possible topics for study.
7. Regularly schedule faculty meetings should be held to discuss problems and/or subjects related to all teacher's situations. The principal should allow teachers to plan these well in advance, inform all of the agenda, and provide for wide participation through organization. Topics should be outgrowth of teacher's felt needs.
8. The principal should require evidence of planning such as submitting lesson plans, reviewing records of students, and having curriculum agenda and minimum learning competencies for each subject taught.
9. Establish rapport with teachers as to methods of incidental supervision and follow – up.

Classroom Observation and Supervision

1. The principal should create an atmosphere for an invitation before his first visit. After the proper rapport is developed between teacher and principal, he may made unscheduled visits.
2. Should the principal fail to get an invitation to visit a teacher, he should ask her to suggest a class and period for him to visit the following week.
3. Acquaint teachers with the purpose of the visit through prior consultation.
4. When visiting, the principal should make himself as inconspicuous as possible. It is desirable that he enters into some phase of the activity if this can be done without undue attention.

5. Make mental notes of strengths and weaknesses for future reference in a conference.
6. Pay close attention to details affecting the teaching – learning situation.
7. A conference should arrange as soon as possible following the visit. Once visited, a teacher wants to know what the principal thinks, and unless a conference is scheduled soon after visit the teacher begins to worry and often feels that the principal was not pleased with what he observed.

Points to be Observed in a Classroom

1. The goals of the lesson being taught: Are these goals reasonable?
2. Instructional techniques being used to achieve goals: Do these techniques provide for individual differences?
3. Is the room ventilated and kept at a reasonable temperature?
4. Is there an evidence of a wholesome atmosphere in the room, a pleasant relationship between the students and teachers?
5. Are students sitting in seats that fit them?
6. Does the teacher allow students to take responsibility for their own learning? Is time provided for individual student work and research?

Fiedler states that successful leader realize that they get their job done through people and therefore try to develop social understanding and appropriate skills. They develop a healthy respect for people. If for no other reason than that, their success depends upon the cooperation of the people. What a leader's real attitudes and values are, he cannot keep them secret. They have a subtle way of being known by his group.

Gagne's recommendation for designing instructions are supported by five assumptions such as "First, instruction should be planned to facilitate the learning of an individual student. Although students are often grouped together for instructions, learning takes place within the individual; therefore, the needs of the learner are placed in the planning sequence prior to grouping. Second, both immediate and long-range are included in the design of instruction. The teacher or instructional designer plans daily lessons, but they occur within the larger segments of units and courses which must also be planned. Third, instructional planning should not be haphazard nor provides merely a nurturing environment. To influence, human development, as much as possible, instructions should be systematically designed using the system approach. The design process should begin with the analysis of needs, continue with the development of goals statement, and then proceed step by step to develop the instruction. Empirical evidence is then obtained about the effectiveness of the instruction in order to revise the material until standards are met. fifth, instruction should be developed from knowledge about how human beings learn.

Bernard, cited the good qualities of a successful school managers based from the subordinate points of news. These are on a good health and physical vitality, endurance, intellectual capacity and material status. He emphasized that good health and vitality reflects good alertness, spring, vigilance and energy while intellectual capacity or attributes is relegated to "brains" as subsidiary to all the other administrative functions.

Administration and supervisory skills as practiced, according to Newman is not a matter of the so called functions, such as the managerial functions which are the sources of the activities of both school leaders and those of the business industries. He stressed that while daily activities, human relation is found as integral part of the whole managerial or supervisory functions.

According to Crew, on Instructional Supervision or school managers to be effective must

be motivated to work beyond medium standards. Knowing the facts that affect the feeling of the teachers about their job is important. Instructional supervisors/managers hold a unique position in nation's system. Whether called consultants or curriculum specialist, they are expected to assist teachers in way that will improve their performance and effectiveness.

The results of the study indicate that the motivation of the school managers is greatly affected by the organizations within which work, the structure of their jobs, their working relationship with others, and support system. School managers who have a sense of accomplishment and feel appreciated are the positions to achieve success in future efforts to improve educational programs. They are caught in a web of negative teacher attitudes of immobilized by poor organization and management.

Kimbrough and Nunnery specified that the school manager's task to provide support for instructional programs. This statement of Kimbrough was clearly included in the present research since it was emphasized that leadership skills of the public secondary school managers be projected along the areas such as providers, resource leaders, communicators, and their visible presence. These qualities or skills of the managers promote quality instructional activities.

Miranda pointed out that leadership and management training for school managers and administrators like the principal must be continuous to enhance educational leadership competencies for a better quality education.

Another similar viewpoint, by Fein who asserted that to achieve increased employee productivity, management must provide the basic conditions which will motivate workers to increase outputs, conditions such as job satisfaction, job security, good pay, good working conditions and financial incentives. Appraising the administrators performance in their present jobs can simply be done through perceptions of several groups of individuals. This is for the purpose of tracing the most outstanding, and the strongest of the weaknesses they are being appraised and are reflected in the evaluation instruments like this present study.

Educational organizations around the world applying total quality management (TQM) reviewed schools, and their findings are revealed and presented below:

In Hungary, the independent High School of Economics at Budapest is apply TQM. The school is striving to create a new educational context for democratic citizenship that has provided a breath of fresh air in a brand of new Republic struggling to understand, and catch up with the past industrial world. The school's process of development focuses on the continuous improvement of all the school community citizens. Their motto, "We are for the tadpoles," reflect the school's profound understanding of the inherent value of being the best possible tadpole, before becoming the best possible frog.

In a small school of Alaska, school leaders apply TQM principles not only to the work for teachers and students in the classrooms but also the establishments of a successful student operated Salmon export business with Japan. The teachers and school boards members tried to convince their superintendent to support TQM and later on succeeded in the endeavor.

In Glenwood, Maryland, a middle school has instituted town meetings for the students where in every students works in one or teams attending the meeting. In teams, students discuss how their work, individually or collectively can be improved, they pledge specific efforts to help bring about the planned results in their houses or class or even the entire school. The team takes projects in the community for public service and town improvements effort at nursing homes and hospitals, at home to improve family life, and at school for campus beautification's.

In East Harlem, with string leadership and vision, the student project demonstrations of

learning progress. Descriptive evaluation of students' work in schools have contributed to the creation of a total quality culture on the challenging environment.

In California, the Redwood Middle Schools in Napa, in solving its problems populations and concomitant tendencies towards impersonalization by creating subgroups of people to discuss the progress of students, to monitor their individual and collective learning process and to plan learning opportunities for students based on analysis of diagnostic test data. Basically it emphasized the team project serious disciplinary problems on transportation of school children have been solved as a results of the efforts of a quality improvement committee composed of parents, bus drivers, transportation supervisor, administrators and students. Moreover, surveys were also conducted in different districts of ascertain whether the internal and external customers of school are satisfied with the kind of services provided or not. These would further strengthen the continuity of total quality practices.

In New Jersey, a state wide project on total quality in the high schools was initiated in order to meet the attendance problem actually faced by them. The budget quality movements in action by using Ishikawa (fishbone) diagram to conduct the cause and effect analysis by brainstorming discussions to find out reasons and searching root cause of students absenteeism. Next, the counter measures potential solutions to those not causes that were within the control to change were listed and using a matrix, effectiveness of each one of its was rated and of course their feasibility in terms of survey, time and so on were recorded. After receiving each and every aspects. The action plan developed and approved by Board of Education.

In Texas, the Arlington Independents School District, has involved the community for reconstituting their school system. They view the schools as an open organization that actively listen to pupils, parents and employees. The communication process is marked by courtesy, responsiveness, and follow up. In the light of suggestion provided, they act positively upon what they learn. Collectively, they strive to make a total quality a continuous process through commitment, bring improvements in all the spheres of the school as an organization.

In Utah, the elementary schools in its quest for quality, made thoughtful improvements in every area of the schools operations, including communication, curriculum and assessments. It however concentrated upon Big Friendly Groups (BFG) including the principal and resource teacher leading the group. The size of the group is then reduced to a smaller group that is, the little friendly groups (LFG) to promote interactions and collegiality. PTA's were also constituted. Specific observations tool to assess quality for both teachers and students were developed. The final area of change for the school was disciplined. All the problematic situations were dealt through open communication between the staff and students without anyone threatening or hunting anyone else. A climate of democratic discipline has been sustained.

In Evan, Colorado, an elementary school used the TQM techniques of data gathering to improve the school writing programme. They built of a "House of Quality" of recording observation using graphic displays. The graphs and charts generated enthusiasm and a picture of improvements for everyone to see including parents and community. Teachers test regroup, tech, test regroup again. Increased collegiality and cross grade collaborations are two benefits of the new writing assessments.

In Australia, a countryside movement fostering school autonomy and school based curriculum developments compatible with greater total improvements was initiated for assessing total quality. In the process, teachers identified areas of concern they spent a great of time discussing their concerns and teaching practice so that activities and ideas were considered and

use by other teachers. The idea were related to teaching techniques and news about students learning and educational change in teacher learning. While teaching, the teachers came to know about students expectations, they accordingly altered their teaching strategies, there were the conditions which facilitated the teaching and learning situations. In this way, the teacher was prepared to examine a common practice in terms of the express value for active learning in the part of the student.

In Ohio, the school staff created a network to promote collaboration and share ideas by forming committees on school visitations, grant research, literature review and distribution publicity resource and training. In each of these meetings the process from the last meeting was reported resulting a significant amount of sharing. The results continue to be rewarding in terms of school collaborations, networking among individuals from diverse school systems, monitoring by knowledgeable total quality management's members, cooperative learning by the members and that sharing of resources. This has been brought about with mutual dedication and keen interest in a collaborative and non-competitive setting.

It is evident to note that the students on TQM results as presented in the preceding pages had dealt on efforts made by the school leaders to assess the performance of all concerned in response to the challenge for quality education, as a necessity of the present times. Similarly, this presents study undertook to evaluate managerial practices that would improve quality outputs.

In another study conducted among 20 Indian school heads by Rashmi, certain indicators to quality improvements came up as highlights in his findings. These are: specific material inputs, teachers qualifications and experiences, school expenditures, teaching practices, students background, community support, competitions, and communications skills among students and staff alike.

Divan's work and the present investigation had similarly using indicators as a measure to quality outcomes of the Universities in Region I through the University Presidents quality in Region I through the University Presidents quality managerial performance which are existing at the time this study was conducted.

The findings of Sallis, presented the difference between quality institution and an ordinary institutions. This is to give a vivid picture of what the quality institutions are like. The summary is hereby included:

Quality Institution	Ordinary Institution
Customers Focused	Focused on Internal Needs
Focused on preventing problems	Focused on Directing Problems
Invest in people	Is not systematic to approach staff development problems
Has a strategy quality	Lack of strategic quality vision
Treats complains as an opportunity to learn	Strategic complains as a nuisance
Has defined the quality characteristics for all areas of the organization	Is vague standard quality
Has a quality policy and plan	Has no quality plans only management terms involved
Management process involve everybody	There is nor quality improvement facilitator

A quality facilitator leads to process	Procedures and rules are all important
Creativity is encourage	Has no systematic strategy
Is clear about roles and responsibility	No clear evaluation strategies
Has clear evaluation strategies	See quality as a means to cutoff cost
Sees quality as a means improve customer's satisfaction	Plans short-term
Plans long term	Is examining quality to meet the demand of internal agency
Is developing quality in time with its own strategic imperative	Has o distinctive missions
Has a distinctive missions	Has a hierarchical culture
Treats colleagues as customers	

Related Studies

Dela Rosa, revealed in her study that teaching is significantly related to the demographic variable, length of advice, designations and educational qualifications.

In another seminar study conducted by Sagay pointed on the performance of administrators is not influenced by a socio-demographic factors. These demographic factors length of service, age, sex, and civil status.

Antiporda, who made an appraisal study found out that the personal related profiles such as age, civil status, sex, and training were not related significantly to academic standards. She also has in her recommendations a continuous evaluation an assessment of the managerial abilities and performance of our school leaders in admit to quality academic standards. This she quoted:

“Through assessment and appraisal system, leaders all know what they are doing, what they should do, and what they should go”.

The three aforementioned studies shed light on the problem number one of the current study. Along these points these studies mentioned are related which had boasted some additional implications drawn as regards to the quality instructional supervisory skills of the secondary school principals or managers particularly in the First Professional District of Pangasinan I.

Soriano, whose study was on Administration and supervisory problems, included variables such as on: supplies and materials, included variables such as on: supplies and materials, school facilities and community relations. Her findings revealed that the degree of seriousness arising on the problems encountered were viewed differently by the respondents. The present study also touched on the seriousness of the problems that affect instructional leadership performance which was included in problem no. 4, and were also viewed differently by the respondent like lack of material time for instructional supervision, poor management of time and resources, poor library facilities and lack of specialization for teachers.

Fernandez, conducted a descriptive profile of the personnel of the Bayambang National High School. The personal and socio-economic characteristics of the teaching and non-teaching personnel their professional qualifications, their attitudes toward their jobs, their interest and aspiration were identified.

Fernandez utilized the descriptive numerative survey method with the questionnaire as a tool for gathering the data.

The study in its final analyses concluded the following:

1. The teaching and non-teaching staff were relatively young, married and female dominated.
2. Pangasinan was the most popular first spoken language of the staff.
3. Majority finished college with the Bachelor degree as their highest educational attainment.
4. Generally, the employees were satisfied with their jobs regardless of their sex, civil status, length of service in the Bayambang National High School, age and status of employment.
5. Majority of the respondents aspired to advance for higher position.

The above study is similarly to this study in the aspect of the background information of the respondents like: the personal attributes that included their civil status, age, sex, designated position as well as their professional background that included their educational qualification, number of teaching experience, scholarship grants, relevant in-service training attended, professional reading materials read, authorship, articles published. Both studies made use of the questionnaire to gain the needed information. The difference between the two studies lies on the fact that Fernandez study focused on the profile of the respondents while this study was not confined with the professional and personal profile of the respondents but on the supervisory skills of the public secondary school managers of Pangasinan I.

In providing effective instructional leadership Mendoza emphasized: What are the characteristics and behavior of an instructional leader?

As an instructional leaders, crystallize your vision of your school – your image of what the school can be and what you want the school to accomplish. You translate it into goals and objectives to be attained. You then focus activities on instructional and the performance of your teachers, and the continuously monitor progress.

It is a truism that good instructional leadership make an effective principal.

The characteristics of an effective principal fall into four categories: leadership traits, problem-solving abilities, social skills and professional knowledge and competence.

Leadership, being the single most powerful determinant of school effectiveness, is manifested through your initiative and resourcefulness, high goal-orientation, flexibility, ability to transform teachers into emerging leaders, willingness to lead and act with courage and deliberation in difficult situation, hardwork and you being proactive rather than reactive.

You utilize your problem-solving and decision-making skills in the course of daily work in schools. You confront problems by analyzing them-looking for cause-effect relationships that might suggest solutions. To promote greater involvement of your staff, you establish a communication system that allows the flow of ideas up and down the line. In this way, the ownership of the problems is shared by all in the school.

You work to establish friendly relations with your staff and at the same time, to maintain leadership authority to earn the respect and willingness to cooperate of your subordinates. You are good-natured, you go out of your way to help teachers. You recognize the private goals of individuals and exert effort to harmonize them with the goals of the school. You are not necessarily born with the desired traits and skills. You develop these. The amount of learning that you gain is proportionate to your desire and determination to upgrade your competencies as an instructional leader.

A handbook of readings for secondary school administrators gave the characteristics and behavior of instructional leaders, to wit:

Observation, common sense, and intuition help formulate an image of a good principal, a strong principal, and an effective principal. Such principals are oftgen referred to in glowing terms: “runs a tight ship”, “sure keeps the parents at bay,” “knows the school inside and out”, or “keeps the school in shape”. However, the imagery seems to be more elusive when we describe the principal as strong instructional leader.

SEDP on instructional leadership on the roles and functions of department heads with respect to instructional supervision enumerates the following:

1. A dynamic process that encourage the interchange of ideas and the interplay of personalities.
2. Is complex and mandates the use of concepts and skills from each dimension: human, managerial, and technical.
3. Is working with people on problems of mutual concern that are related to the structure of the school as an organization.
4. Involves the systematic study and analysis of the entire teaching-learning situation utilizing a carefully planned program that has been cooperatively derived from the situation and which is adapted to the needs of those involved in it.
5. Involves analysis of teaching, technology, efficiency and effectiveness measures, accountability program, management of human resources, support system for the work of teachers and instructional development.
6. Is a key link between the goal system of the organization and the teaching system.
7. Has built-in accountability; supervisory accountability, organizational accountability, and accountability to the larger profession.

Accountability entails ethical as well as organizational connotations; as a professional, a supervisor has the ethical responsibility for competence.

8. Recognizes that the person with highly developed human skills is aware of his own attitudes, assumptions, and beliefs about other individuals and groups; he is able to see the usefulness and limitations of these feelings. My accepting the existence of viewpoints, perceptions, and belief which are different from his own, he is skillfull in understanding what others really mean by their words and behavior.

A department head is responsible to his or her own competence and continued learning. Competence implies growth, continued learning and professional self-renewal. Knowing and analyzing his/her job, identifying his/her roles and functions is a “linking pin” in the organizational set-up would make the supervisor receptive to professional growth and self-renewal.

Aquino states that the key element in the administrative processes are people. This holds true whether the administrative process is applied to any fields of administration. If the key element in the administration process is people, then the process. It is a social process in terms of objectives since its desired end is the social development of the whole individual. In terms of content, it is a social process because the substance of the subject matter in its decision making function involves or affects people directly or indirectly. In terms of methods, it is a social process since it utilizes procedures, strategies, processes and techniques which involves or affects human being directly or indirectly.

He further stated that administrative functions can further be understood if we look at it

in the complementary view: the foundational view poses the issue of why one behaves as he does and it utilizes establish and emerging theoretical framework for analyzing the antecedents, predictors, and correlates outcomes of administrative behavior. The functional view, on the other had poses the issue of what one does or should do as an administrator, and it focuses on the tasks and activities in which one must be competent if he is to be an effective administrator.

Rev. Fr. Paul Zwaenepoel for instance presented several factors which may serve as guideline in the performance of one's administrative work. That administrative could be more enjoyable and benefiting if administrators and the people they work with are very conscious of few dimension in administration service which could be substituted for the status symbol of practice. Administration powers, rights, and responsibility should not make the administration an opportunist of favors and advantages attached to his office. He should not expect to be attended to, but serve others, not to withhold all the powers of his personal aggrandizement, but not to the extent these to many people as possible. This is administration sharing and serving in higher capacity and responsibility.

Llagas, in her contribution to instructional leadership said that instructional leaders should posses qualities that would enable them to work with people above them and below them. Competence areas identified as Skills Mix (SM) are categorized as follows: human, managerial and technical skills.

Human skills include translating or interpreting organization goals to generate teachers commitment; responding to individual differences; diagnosing of individual strength and potential; clarifying values' conducting group discussion; resolving conflict maintaining sound public relations and stimulating cooperation among staff members.

Managerial skills include assessing teachers needs; establishing instructional priorities for the instruction of change, advocacy of new curricula, innovative methods, new technology; analyzing educational environment; delegating responsibilities; managing time; monitoring and/or controlling activities and documenting organization and instructional activities.

Technical skills include using classroom observation system, analyzing classroom observation data; categorizing and clustering instructional objectives; establishing criteria for the selection of instructional materials; applying research findings; analyzing instructional setting; developing evaluation procedure; analyzing instructional tasks and demonstrating instructional skills and practices.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the description of the methods used, and locale and population of the study, the instruments used, the procedure and the treatment of the data in this study.

Methodology/Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive method. Specifically, the descriptive normative survey was used to answer the questionnaire which was instrumental in gathering the data needed. The data were gathered, interpreted and analyzed. These were further treated to a descriptive as well as inferential analysis. To test the significance and the difference of the variables based on perceived results, the T'test was used as the statistical tool.

Locale and Population of the Study

This study was conducted among the existing public secondary school administrators and teachers. There were 215 from 11-A and 162 from II-B, 45 of them were male and 90 were female. While on the secondary school administrators who are the Principals, Head Teachers from the said district were composed of thirty with different ranks like principal I and II and secondary Head Teachers I or department heads. Please refer to the table 1 next page.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher used a questionnaire to obtain the necessary data from the instructional training for department heads, It contained items such as: Background information like: personal attribute and professional background; instructional leadership skills as provider, resource leaders, as communicators and as visible presence, extent to which the managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills; and extent of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance.

Validation of the Questionnaire

The instrument was reviewed by the experts in educational leadership parlance whose comments and suggestions were all incorporated.

The content validity of the instruments and used was established by trying the instruments to the secondary school administrators with a total 20 school managers and 80 faculty members. Subsequent corrections and suggestions were further included. It was submitted to the researcher's adviser for further corrections and suggestions as well as proper editing and then finally approved for used as drafted by the researcher. Copies were reproduced and distributed to the respondents.

Administration of the Questionnaire

Permission to administer the questionnaire was sought from the Division Schools Superintendent of Pangasinan I and the school principals of the secondary schools covered by the study. The researcher administered personally the questionnaire to the said respondents which took her one month to retrieve them one hundred percent.

Chapter 3

PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data gathered through the questionnaire particularly on the background information of the respondents and their leadership skills of the public secondary school heads.

However, the instructional leadership skills of the respondents included the following salient points: as provider, as a resources leader, as a communicator, and as visible presence. It also discussed how the school head perform their roles to enhance leadership skills and the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance.

Table 1.a
Extent of Realization of the Leadership Skills as Perceived
by the School Managers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
A. As Provider	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Plans, makes, schedules and prioritizes work to be accomplished in school.	23(92)	3 9	3 6	1 1	108	3.60	VS
2. Assigns teachers according to their field of specialization.	24(96)	3 8	2 4	1 1	110	3.67	VS
3. Establishes goals and objectives that teachers and students expect to achieve.	20(80)	5 15	4 8	1 1	104	3.47	VS
4. Delegates work appropriate to their expertise skills.	22(88)	5 15	1 2	2 2	108	3.60	VS
5. Provides a positive working climate for change.	15(60)	10 30	5 10	0 0	100	3.33	FS

6. Uses leadership skills needed to effect challenge.	21(84)	7 21	2 4	0 0	109	3.63	FS
7. Evaluates the effectiveness of change.	10(40)	14 42	4 8	2 2	92	3.07	FS
8. Encourages staff to take risks and to make innovations.	14(56)	14 42	1 2	1 1	101	3.37	FS
9. Matches staff member's needs to staff development opportunities.	15(60)	11 33	4 8	0 0	101	3.37	FS
10. Utilizes resources that enhance effective instruction.	20(80)	9 27	1 2	0 0	109	3.63	VS
11. Mobilizes resources and school support to help achieve academic objectives set.	23(92)	3 9	4 8	0 0	109	3.63	VS
12. Convinces staff members that they are important instructional resources in school.	25(100)	4 12	1 2	0 0	114	3.80	VS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.51	VS

Legend:	Arbitrary Value	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Value
	1	3.41 – 4.20	Very Satisfactory = VS
	2	2.61 – 3.40	Fairly Satisfactory = FS
	3	1.81 – 2.60	Satisfactory = S
	4	1.00 – 1.80	Poor = P

As provider, it included his jobs like making plans, schedule and prioritization of work to be accomplished, assigning teachers, establishing goals, an objectives, delegating works, providing positive working climate, using leadership skills, evaluating change, encouraging staffs to make innovations, matching member needs to staff development opportunities, utilizing

resources and school support, mobilizing resources, and communicating to staff members that they are important instructional resources in school. It could be seen in table 1 that providing plans schedules, and prioritizing work to be accomplished in school was given a total weighted point of 108 with an average weighted point of 3.60 which was described as very satisfactory. The others which were described as very satisfactory. The others which were described very satisfactory were: assigns teachers according to their field of specialization with a total weighted point of 110 and average weighted point of 3.67; uses leadership skills needed to effect change with a total weighted point of 109 and average weighted point of 3.63; utilizes resources that enhance effective instruction with a total weighted point of 109 and average weighted point of 3.63; mobilizes resources and school support to help achieve academic objectives with a total weighted point of 109 and average weighted point of 3.63; and convinces staff members that they are important instructional resources in school with a total weighted point of 114 and average weighted point of 3.80. There were four which was rated fairly satisfactory and these were the effectiveness of change with an average weighted point of 3.07; provides positive working climate with an average weighted point of 3.33; encourages staff to take risks and to make innovations with a weighted point of 3.37; matches staff members needs to staff development opportunities with an average weighted point of 3.37.

The table could give us a picture of the extent of realization of the leadership skills of the school manager as a provider which it was very satisfactory as revealed by the total weighted average point of 3.51.

This implied that the school managers should maintain and continue to dispense their leadership skills as provider. It could imply further that these manager were good and skillful leaders as provider. This skill if devotedly and responsibly executed, then institution will eventually be improved. However, there was still a great need to improve the fairly satisfactory aspects described by them so as to smoothly perform such skills effectively.

Table 1.b presents another important leadership skills of the school manager which is on the instruction resources leader which could initiate the teachers to improve and update their teaching-learning activities.

This instructional resources leaders was composed of the task of the school managers to inform/share teachers of the latest research finding, share/use his knowledge of effective teaching strategies, demonstrate to write curriculum goals and objective, conducts pre and post observation conference, provide teachers with evidence of continuity of clinical supervisory documents instructional performance of teacher, effectively with teacher regarding students performances, assists teachers in the mastery of having, interprets and utilizes school criteria's reference test, communicate to staff parents, and community, design appropriate evaluation measures, and develop intervention measures designed to identify and remedy weakness and enhance strengths.

Table 1.b
Extent of Realization of the Leadership Skills as Instructional Resources as Perceived by School Managers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
B. As Instructional Resources Leader	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Informs / shares teachers with the latest re-search findings on teaching and learning to be tried in their classes.	20 80	10 30	0 0	0 0	110	3.67	VS
2. Shares/uses his knowledge of effective teaching strategies appropriate for different age level.	20 80	10 30	0 0	0 0	110	3.67	VS
3. Demonstrates the ability to write curriculum goals/objective.	18 72	10 30	2 4	0 0	106	3.53	VS
4. Conducts pre and post observation conferences that include developmental objectives suggested by small staff member.	20 80	7 21	3 6	0 0	107	3.57	VS
5. Provides teachers with evidence of continuity of clinical supervision / observation.	14 56	10 30	4 8	2 2	96	3.20	FS
6. Documents instructional	20 80	7 21	3 6	0 0	107	3.57	VS

performance of teachers.							
7. Confers effectively with teachers regarding student's performances.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
8. Assists teachers in the mastery of student learning objectives.	14 56	10 30	5 10	1 1	97	3.23	FS
9. Interprets and utilizes school criterion references tests and other results to improve instruction.	15 60	9 27	4 8	2 2	97	3.23	FS
10. Communicates to staff, parents, and community the extent to which learning objectives have been mastered by students.	20 80	6 18	3 6	1	105	3.50	VS
11. Designs appropriate evaluation measures to include effective goal setting with teachers and appropriate measurement of these goals.	14 56	10 30	6 12	0 0	98	3.27	FS
12. Develops intervention measures designed to identify and remedy	13 52	11 33	6 12	0 0	97	3.23	FS

weaknesses and enhance strengths.							
Total Average Weighted Point						3.43	VS

As we look at table closely it could be gleaned that to inform, share teachers with the latest research finding on teaching learning to be tried in their classes was given at a total weighted point of 110 and average weighted point of 3.67 which was described as very satisfactorily. To share or use his knowledge of effective teaching strategies appropriate for different age level was given a total weighted point of 110 and average weighted point of 3.67 described a very satisfactory. On the demonstrate the ability to write curriculum goals or objectives it was given a total weighted point of 106 and average weighted point of 3.53 which was described as very satisfactory. To conduct pre and post observation conference it was rated very satisfactory with a total weighted point of 107 and average weighted point of 3.57. However, to provide teacher with evidence of continuity of clinical supervision was rated fairly satisfactory as evidenced by the total weighted point of 96 or average weighted mean of 3.20. Documents instructional performance of teachers was given a total weighted point of 107 and average of 3.57 which was described a very satisfactory with a total weighted point of 106 and average 3.53. To assists teachers in the mastery of students learning objective was given a total weighted point of 97 and average weighted point of 3.23 described fairly satisfactory. Then to interpret and utilizes school criticism performance test was rated fairly satisfactory with a total weighted point of 3.23. Communicate to staff, parents and community the extent of learning objective was rated very satisfactory as evidence by the total weighted point of 105 and average weighted point of 3.50. Design appropriate evaluation measure to include effective goal setting with teacher was given a total weighted point of 98 and average point of 3.27 which was described as fairly satisfactory poor, lastly, develop interaction measure to identify and remedy weakness and strength was fairly satisfactory proven by the total weighted point of 97 and average weighted point of 3.23.

The total would imply that based from the findings that the school managers concern should improve the aspects on providing teachers with evidences of continuity of clinical supervision; assisting teachers in the mastery of student learning objectives; interpreting and utilizing school interior referenced tests; designing appropriate evaluation measures to include effective goal setting with teachers, and developing information measures from fairly satisfactory to very satisfactory, since there were some significant factors to enhance instruction qualitatively as revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.43 which was very satisfactory this would say that the managers were skillful in the aspect of instructional resources.

Table 1.c shows one of the most beneficial leadership skills of the school manager which is on effective communicator.

The table presents the 12 ways on how the school managers translated their job as a communicator and the extent of realization of these skills by the 30 respondents from the different public secondary school in the first congressional district of Pangasinan.

Table 1.c
Leadership Skills as Communicator as Perceived by the School Head

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
C. As Communicator	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Develops a system of an open Communication.	16 64	8 24	4 8	2 2	98	3.27	FS
2. Demonstrates competence in oral and written communication.	18 72	8 24	2 4	2 2	102	3.40	FS
3. Manifests good information organizational skills in oral and written communication.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
4. Recognizes and knows what information is appropriate to communicate which promote mutual conflicts.	20 80	5 15	5 10	0 0	105	3.50	VS
5. Displays the ability to help others and arrives at mutually acceptable solution.	20 80	5 15	4 8	1 1	104	3.47	VS
6. Recognizes needs and interacts appropriately with specific clientele in the educational community.	15 60	8 24	6 12	1 1	97	3.23	FS
7. Identifies, collects, analyses and used valid,	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS

relevant and reliable information to assess current situation.							
8. Provides a written, uniform disciplinary program for the school.	16 64	9 27	4 8	1 1	100	3.33	FS
9. Demonstrates the ability to integrate group and personal.	14 56	11 33	3 6	2 2	97	3.23	FS
10. Demonstrate strong group process skills.	11 44	12 36	5 10	2 2	102	3.40	FS
11. Develops an implementation plan that includes provisions for evaluation process and outcomes.	13 52	13 39	2 4	2 2	97	3.23	FS
12. Gives and encourages feedback's about the performance of teachers.	20 80	8 24	1 2	1 1	107	3.57	VS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.39	FS

On the develop system of an open communication, it was described as fairly satisfactory with a total weighted point of 98, and average weighted point of 3.27. For demonstrates competence in oral and written communication, it was given a total weighted point of 102 and average weighted point of 3.40 which was described as fairly satisfactory. Manifest good information is appropriate to communicate which promote mutual conflicts, resolution, problem solving, cooperation, and sharing was given a total weighted point of 105 and average weighted point of 3.5 which was described as very satisfactory; displays the ability to help others and arrive at mutually acceptable solution was given a total weighted point of 104 and average weighted point of 3.47 which was described as very satisfactory; recognizes needs and interacts appropriately with specific clientele in the educational community was given a total weighted point of 97 and average weighted point of 3.23 which was described as fairly satisfactory; identifies, collects, analyzes and used valid, relevant and reliable information to asses current situation was given a total weighted point of 106 and average weighted point of 3.53 described

as very satisfactory; provides a written, uniform disciplinary program for the school had a total weighted point of 100 and average weighted point of 3.33 described as fairly satisfactory; demonstrate the ability to integrate group and personal goals had a total weighted point of 97 and average weighted point of 102 and described as fairly satisfactory, demonstrate strong group process skills had a total weighted point of 102 and average weighted point of 3.40 with a description of fairly satisfactory; develops an implementation that includes procedure for evaluation process and outcome was described as fairly satisfactory revealed by the total weighted point of 97 and average weighted point of 3.23; and gives and encourages feedbacks about the performances of teachers had a total weighted point of 107 and average weighted point of 3.57 with a description of very satisfactory.

It could be noted clearly that 7 of the 12 points on as communicator were rated fairly satisfactory. These were develop, system of an open communication, recognizes needs and interacts appropriately, and develop an implementation plan, develop competence in oral and written communication; provides a written, uniform disciplinary program for the school; demonstrate strong group process skilled; develops an implementation plan that includes provisions for evaluation process and outcomes.

The table implied that there was a great need of improving the aspects which were rated fairly satisfactory to very satisfactory. In this sense, these school managers concern would become very effective and qualitatively perform their roles as school managers and leaders as revealed by the total weighted average point of 3.39 described fairly satisfactory. The further implication of this therefore is that the success of leadership of this managers depends greatly on their ability to communicate to the subordinate. They should be adapt to this aspect very satisfactory.

Table 1.d reveals leadership skills of the secondary managers as visible presence perceived by themselves.

Looking at the table closely, it could be gleaned that out of the 12 items considered under visible presence 11 were rated very satisfactory. These were: expresses a clear vision for the school and community with teachers before formulating the school mission with a weighted average point of 3.57; manifests since commitment to the priority goals of the school with average weighted point of 3.53; buffers the school from external environment with an average weighted point of 3.53; and finally communicates clearly the responsibilities of teacher with an average weighted point of 3.53. Three of the items under visible presence were rated poor. There were: organizers people and material resources to accomplish goals with an average weighted point of 3.47; manifest behavior consistent with articulated mission of the school with an average weighted point of 3.43, and lastly checks teachers daily teaching preparation early in the morning and in the afternoon with an average weighted point of 3.37 which was rated fairly satisfactory.

Table 1.d
Leadership Skills as Visible Presence as Perceived by School Heads

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
D. As Visible Presence	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Express a clear vision for the school.	20 80	7 21	3 6	0 0	107	3.57	VS
2. Organizers people and material resources to accomplish goals.	18 72	8 24	4 8	0 0	104	3.47	VS
3. Conducts needs assessment in the school and community.	20 80	7 21	3 6	0 0	107	3.57	VS
4. Involves self actively in all school activities.	24 96	4 12	1 2	1 1	111	3.70	VS
5. Manifest behavior consistent with the articulated mission of the school.	20 80	5 15	4 8	1 1	103	3.43	VS
6. Participates in the staff development activities of teachers.	20 80	8 24	1 2	0 0	107	3.57	VS
7. Manages time to be "out and around" during school hours.	25 100	5 15	0 0	1 1	117	3.90	VS
8. Checks teachers daily teaching preparation early in the morning and in the	16 64	10 30	3 6	1 1	101	3.37	FS

afternoon.							
9. Drops into classroom informally without disrupting the instructional process.	18 72	11 33	1 2	0 0	107	3.57	VS
10. Manifest sincere commitment to the priority goals of the school.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
11. Buffers the school from external environment.	19 76	8 24	3 6	0 0	106	3.53	VS
12. Communicates clearly the responsibilities of teachers.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.56	VS

The table give a clear perceptions that the secondary school mangers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan very satisfactorily exemplify their job as instructional leaders with their visible presence as proven by the total average weighted point of 356. The findings implied further that the school managers should look into the significance of their visible presence in carrying out proper instructions in the school from being very satisfactory. They should therefore workout for the upliftment of the realization of the leadership skill as visible presence and use it as their strengths in quality dispensation of leadership skills. this would imply further that with their visible presence that activities especially on instructions could be guided accordingly.

Table 2.a shows the leadership skills of the school managers as provider as perceived by the teachers.

Table 2.a
Leadership Skills as Providers Perceived by Teachers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
A. As Provider	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weight ed Point	Averag e Weight ed Point	Descripti ve Equivalen t
1. Plans, makes, schedules and prioritizes work to be accomplished in school.	89 356	30 90	15 30	1 1	477	3.53	VS
2. Assigns teachers according to their field of specialization.	87 348	37 111	10 20	1 1	480	3.56	VS
3. Establishes goals and objectives that teachers and students expect to achieve.	86 344	29 87	17 34	3 3	468	3.47	VS
4. Delegates work appropriate to their expertise skills.	85 340	33 99	17 34	1 1	474	3.51	VS
5. Provides a positive working climate for change.	65 260	41 123	26 52	3 3	438	3.24	FS
6. Uses leadership skills needed to effect challenge.	66 264	43 129	22 44	8 8	445	3.30	FS
7. Evaluates the effectiveness of change.	61 244	43 129	22 44	5 5	425	3.15	FS
8. Encourages staff to take risks and to make innovations.	66 264	41 123	23 46	3 3	438	3.24	FS
9. Matches staff member's needs	63 252	46 138	23 46	3 3	439	3.25	FS

to staff development opportunities.							
10. Utilizes resources that enhance effective instruction.	66 264	44 132	22 44	3 3	443	3.28	FS
11. Mobilizes resources and school support to help achieve academic objectives set.	73 292	42 126	16 32	4 4	454	3.36	FS
12. Convinces staff members that they are important instructional resources in school.	75 300	39 117	19 38	2 2	457	3.38	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.36	FS

There were 135 secondary school teachers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan who rated the extent of realization of the leadership skills as provider as perceived by the teachers. The factors included in the table were: plans, makes schedule and prioritizes work to be accomplished in school was very satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.53; assigns teachers according to their field of specialization was described very satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.56; establishes goals and objectives that teachers and students expect to achieve was given an average weighted point of 3.56; establishes goals and objectives that teachers and students expect to achieve was given an average weighted point of 3.56; establishes goals and objectives that teachers and students expect to achieve was given an average weighted point of 3.47 described as very satisfactory; delegates work appropriate to their expertise was rated very satisfactory with an average weighted point 3.51; provides a positive working climate for change was described fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.24; uses leadership skills needed to effect change was described fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.30; evaluates the effectiveness of change was described fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.15; encourages staff to take risks and to make innovations was also rated fairly satisfactory too with an average weighted point of 3.25; utilizes resources that enhances effective instruction was also rated fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.28; mobilizes resources and school support to help achieve academic objectives set was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.36, and finally convinces staff members that they are important instructional resources in school was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.38.

Analyzing the table completely, it could be perceived that the extent of realization of the

leadership skills of the school manager as perceived by the teacher was fairly satisfactory as proven by the total average weighted point 3.36. Further this implied that they were good provider, however there should be a great need of improving, the weakest aspects like evaluate the effectiveness of change and encourages staff to take risks and to make innovations and all others which were rated fairly satisfactory to very satisfactory.

Table 2.b presents the leadership skills of the managers as instructional resources leaders perceived by leaders.

There were 135 secondary school teachers who rated the extent of realization of the leadership skill of the school manager as instructional resources leader wherein 12 factors were under it were rationally considered.

Table 2.b
Extent of Realization of the Leadership Skills as Instructional Resources as Perceived by Teachers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
B. As Instructional Resources Leader	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Informs / shares teachers with the latest re-search findings on teaching and learning to be tried in their classes.	21 84	36 108	18 36	10 10	438	3.24	VS
2. Shares/uses his knowledge of effective teaching strategies appropriate for different age level.	65 260	44 132	19 38	7 7	437	3.23	FS
3. Demonstrates the ability to write curriculum goals/objective.	63 252	46 138	17 34	9 9	433	3.21	FS
4. Conducts pre and post observation conferences that include	70 280	39 117	22 44	4 4	445	3.30	FS

developmental objectives suggested by small staff member.							
5. Provides teachers with evidence of continuity of clinical supervision / observation.	57 228	40 120	29 58	9 9	415	3.07	FS
6. Documents instructional performance of teachers.	74 296	34 102	22 44	5 5	447	3.31	FS
7. Confers effectively with teachers regarding student's performances.	82 328	26 78	22 44	5 5	455	3.37	FS
8. Assists teachers in the mastery of student learning objectives.	67 268	39 117	21 42	8 8	435	3.22	FS
9. Interprets and utilizes school criterion references tests and other results to improve instruction.	69 276	39 117	19 38	8 8	439	3.25	FS
10. Communicates to staff, parents, and community the extent to which learning objectives have been mastered by students.	75 300	36 108	21 42	3 3	453	3.36	FS
11. Designs appropriate evaluation measures to	64 256	45 135	21 42	5 5	438	3.24	FS

include effective goal setting with teachers and appropriate measurement of these goals.							
12. Develops intervention measures designed to identify and remedy weaknesses and enhance strengths.	62 248	41 123	26 52	6 6	429	3.18	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.25	FS

These were: informs / shares teachers with the latest research findings on teaching and learning to be tried in their classes was rated 3.24 described as 'fairly satisfactory'; shares his knowledge of effective teaching strategies appropriate for different age level was described as 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.23; demonstrate the ability to write curriculum goals and objectives was rated 3.21 described as 'fairly satisfactory'; conducts pre and post observation conferences was rated 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.30; provides teachers with continuity of clinical supervision/observation was rated 'fairly satisfactory' as evidenced by an average weighted point of 3.07; documents instructional performance of teachers was described as 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.31 confers effectively with teachers regarding students performance was described as 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.37; assists teachers in the mastery of students learning objectives was 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.22; interprets and utilizes school criterion reference tests was described as 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.25; communicates to staff, parents, and community the extent to which learning objectives has been mastered by student was rated 'fairly satisfactory' with an average point of 3.36; designs appropriate evaluation measures to include effective goal setting with teachers was described as 'fairly satisfactory' with an average weighted point of 3.24; finally, develops intervention measures designed to identify and remedy weaknesses and enhance strengths was given an average weighted point of 3.18 described as 'fairly satisfactory'.

Looking at the table it could be clearly gleaned that the school manager's leadership skills as instructional leader was 'fairly satisfactory' as proven by the total average weighted point of 3.25. The table implied that there would still be a need of strengthening their skill as instructional resources leaders from 'fairly satisfactory' to 'very satisfactory' especially in the 'fairly satisfactory' areas like provides teachers with evidences of continuity of clinical supervision or observation and demonstrate the ability to write curriculum goals and objectives as well as develops intervention measures designed to identify remedy weaknesses and enhance strengths. Basically the findings implied further that the school manager need to upgrade and compare their leadership skills as resources leader which is very essential especially so that there are crises on

facilities, materials, equipment's and financial resources to finance any activities of the school.

Table 2.c shows the leadership skills of 59. The managers as communicator perceived by the teachers.

There were 12 factors included in the aspect of the extent of the leadership skills of the school manager as communicator rated by the 135 secondary school teachers.

These factors were as follows: developed a system of an open communication described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.32; demonstrate competence in oral and written communication was rated 3.27 described as fairly satisfactory; manifests good information organizational skills in oral and written communication was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.37; recognizes and knows what information is appropriate to communicate was described as fairly satisfactory proven by the average weighted point of 3.21; displays the ability to help others and arrives at mutually acceptable solution was given an average weighted point of 3.37 described as fairly satisfactory; recognizes needs and interacts appropriately with specific clientele in the educational community was fairly satisfactory described with an average weighted point of 3.22; identifies, collects, analyzes and uses valid, relevant and reliable information to assess current situations was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.27; demonstrate the ability to integrate group and personal goals was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.25; demonstrate a strong group process skills described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.22; develops an implementation plan that includes provisions for evaluation process and outcomes was described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.16; and finally gives and encourages feedbacks about the performance of teachers was described fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.24.

Table 2.c
Leadership Skills as Communicator as Perceived by Teachers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
C. As Communicator	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Develops a system of an open Communication	72 288	38 114	22 44	3 3	449	3.32	FS
2. Demonstrates competence in oral and written communication.	67 268	43 129	19 38	6 6	441	3.27	FS
3. Manifests good information organizational skills in oral and written	74 296	41 123	16 32	4 4	455	3.37	FS

communication.							
4. Recognizes and knows what information is appropriate to communicate which promote mutual conflicts.	61 244	46 138	23 46	5 5	433	3.21	FS
5. Displays the ability to help others and arrives at mutually acceptable solution.	73 292	40 120	18 36	5 5	455	3.37	FS
6. Recognizes needs and interacts appropriately with specific clientele in the educational community.	65 260	41 123	23 46	6 6	435	3.22	FS
7. Identifies, collects, analyses and used valid, relevant and reliable information to assess current situation.	68 272	39 117	20 40	8 8	437	3.24	FS
8. Provides a written, uniform disciplinary program for the school.	71 284	39 117	16 32	9 9	442	3.27	FS
9. Demonstrates the ability to integrate group and personal.	68 272	39 117	22 44	6 6	439	3.25	FS
10. Demonstrate strong group process skills.	62 248	44 123	26 52	3 3	455	3.22	FS
11. Develops an implementation plan that includes	63 252	39 117	24 48	9 9	426	3.16	FS

provisions for evaluation process and outcomes.							
12. Gives and encourages feedback's about the performance of teachers.	63 252	45 135	23 46	4 4	437	3.24	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.43	FS

The table could clearly suggest that the school managers extent of realization of their leadership skills as communicators was fairly satisfactory as proven or indicated by the total average point of 3.26. The table could imply that the school managers should aspire to improve the factors as they were rated fairly satisfactory like recognizes the needs appropriately, identifies, collects and analyzes the valid relevant information and develops implementation plan that include provision for evaluation process and outcomes, since they were perceived by the teachers as fairly satisfactory which may affect the attitude and behavior of the teachers especially on their trust and respect to their school manager's credibility, capability and copability. Thus, it would foster understanding and better performance of their work if they understand the message, confirmation and institution communicated.

The table presents the extent of the leadership skills as visible presence perceived by the teachers. There were 12 factors considered by the respondents.

Table 2.d

Extent of Realization of the Leadership Skills as Visible Presence as Perceived by Teachers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
D. As Visible Presence	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weight ed Point	Averag e Weight ed Point	Descript ive Equival ent
1. Express a clear vision for the school.	89 356	33 99	11 22	2 2	479	3.55	VS
2. Organizers people and material resources to accomplish goals.	75 300	37 111	15 30	8 8	449	3.32	FS
3. Conducts needs assessment in the school and community.	65 260	40 120	26 52	4 4	436	3.23	FS

4. Involves self actively in all school activities.	86 344	30 90	13 26	6 6	466	3.45	VS
5. Manifest behavior consistent with the articulated mission of the school.	78 312	35 105	17 34	5 5	456	3.38	FS
6. Participates in the staff development activities of teachers.	87 348	32 96	13 26	3 3	473	3.5	VS
7. Manages time to be "out and around" during school hours.	82 328	28 84	20 40	5 5	457	3.38	FS
8. Checks teachers daily teaching preparation early in the morning and in the afternoon.	67 68	44 132	16 32	8 8	440	3.36	FS
9. Drops into classroom informally without disrupting the instructional process.	72 288	40 120	17 34	6 6	448	3.32	FS
10. Manifest sincere commitment to the priority goals of the school.	83 332	32 96	17 34	3 3	465	3.44	VS
11. Buffers the school from external environment.	80 320	38 114	10 120	2 2	456	3.38	FS
12. Communicates clearly the responsibilities of teachers.	80 320	36 108	17 34	2 2	464	3.34	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.38	FS

It could be noted in the table that there were 8 of the factors that were rated fairly satisfactory. These were: Organizes people and material resources to accomplish goals with an average weighted point of 3.32 described as fairly satisfactory; conducts needs assessment in the school and community with teachers before formulating the school mission with an average weighted point of 13.23 described as fairly satisfactory checks teachers daily teaching preparation early in the morning and in the afternoon with an average weighted points of 3.26 described as fairly satisfactory; manifests behavior consistent with the articulated mission of the school with an average weighted point of 3.38 described as fairly satisfactory; drops into classroom informally without disrupting the instruction process with an average weighted point of 3.32 described as fairly satisfactory; manages time to be out and around during school hours with an average weighted point of 3.38 described as fairly satisfactory; manifests sincere commitment to the priority goals of the school with an average weighted point of 3.44 described as fairly satisfactory; and finally; communicates clearly the responsibilities of teaches with an average weighted point of 3.44 described as fairly satisfactory.

Looking at the table closely it could be noted that there were two factors under visible presence which were rated very satisfactory. These were: expresses a clear vision for the school with an average weighted point of 3.55; and participates in the staff development activities of teachers with an average weighted point of 3.50.

The table manifest a clear picture of the extent of realization of the leadership skills as visible presence as perceived by the teachers which was fairly satisfactory revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.39.

This implied further that the visible presence of the school managers which could be considered as one of the essentials of instruction should be given emphasis and direction.

Table 3 presents the roles which the school heads performed to enhance leadership skills perceived by themselves.

Table 3
Extent of Realization to which the School Managers Performs their Roles to Enhance Leadership Skills as Perceived by School Managers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
School Mangers' Role to Enhance Leadership Skills	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. An organizer, skillful in establishing various kinds of programs of values to teachers.	18 72	8 24	3 6	1 1	103	3.43	VS
2. A master teacher, able to demonstrate effective / good	16 64	6 18	6 12	2 2	96	3.20	FS

teaching.							
3. A strong leader, who knows how to work with groups and get the most of it.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
4. A stimulator, who suggest ideas for teachers to consider.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
5. A coordinator, who seeks to achieve articulation which programs, level and helps teachers become aware of each other's problem.	18 72	10 30	2 4	0 0	89	2.47	S
6. As orientor, who takes responsibility for helping teachers who are new to the system and community to become acquainted.	20 80	8 24	1 2	1 1	107	3.57	VS
7. As consultant, who responds to individual teachers needing his expertise.	20 80	7 21	2 4	1 1	106	3.53	VS
8. A public relation person, who may be involved to interpret the curriculum to the public.	18 72	9 27	2 4	1 1	104	3.47	VS
9. A researcher, who conducts action research.	9 36	12 36	6 12	3 3	87	2.90	FS
10. A change agent, a catalyst for helping teacher to change and improve.	14 56	9 27	4 8	3 3	94	3.13	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.28	FS

The group of 30, school managers were asked about the extent of realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills whether very satisfactory, fairly

satisfactory, satisfactory and poor.

It could be seen in table 3 that 6 out of 10 items on their roles were rated very satisfactory. an organizer, skillful in establishing various kind of values to teachers was rated very satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.43; a strong leader who knows how to work with groups and get the most of it had an average weighted point of 3.53 which was very satisfactory, as orientor takes responsibility for helping teachers who are new to the system and community was rated very satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.57; as consultant, who responds to individual teaches needing his expertise was given an average weighted point of 3.53 described as very satisfactory; and public relations person, who may be invited to interpret the curriculum to the public was rated 3.47 was very satisfactory. As coordinator, who seeks to achieve articulation with programs, levels, and helps teachers become aware of each other's problem was rated 2.47 described as satisfactory followed by a researcher who conducts action research with an average weighted point of 2.90 described as fairly satisfactory, then a master teacher able to demonstrate effective, good teaching described as fairly satisfactory with an average weighted point of 3.20; and finally a change agent, a catalyst for helping teachers to change and improve was described as fairly satisfactory with an average total weighted point of 3.13.

The table implied that although the school managers perform their roles fairly satisfactory, they still need to improve the areas on the aspect of being coordinator and researcher, change agent, as well as master teachers who demonstrate effective of good teaching. It could be necessary then that these managers should perform their roles to enhance leadership skills religiously since they are considered the masters of their job, duties and responsibilities.

Table 4 shows the roles which the school managers perform to enhance leadership skills perceived by the teachers.

There were 10 factors considered in the realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills.

Out of these 10 factors, 1 of them was rated very satisfactory. This was: a strong leader, who knows how to work with groups and get the most of it with an average weighted point of 3.41. However, the rest of the 10 items were rated fairly satisfactory; a stimulator who suggest ideas for teachers to consider with, an average weighted point of 3.32 fairly satisfactory; as orientor who takes responsibility for helping teachers who are new to the system and community to become acquitted with an average weighted point of 3.30 very satisfactory; as organizer, skillful in establishing various kinds of programs of values to teachers with an average weighted point of 3.27 fairly satisfactory; master teacher, who is able to demonstrate effective good teaching with an average weighted point of 3.18 (fairly satisfactory), a coordinator, who seeks to achieve articulation which programs, levels and help teachers become aware of each other's problem with an average weighted point of 3.27 (fairly satisfactory); as consultant, who responds to individual teacher needing his expertise with an average weighted point of 3.27 (fairly satisfactory); a public relation person, who may be invited to interpret the curriculum to the public with an average weighted point of 3.21 (fairly satisfactory); and finally, a change agent, who is a catalyst for helping teachers to change and improve with an average weighted point of 3.25 (fairly satisfactory); and finally, a change, agent, who is a catalyst for helping teachers to change and improve with an average weighted point of 3.25 (fairly satisfactory).

Looking at the table closely, it could be noted that there were was no factor that was rated satisfactory and only 1 was described very satisfactory.

The table therefore could give us a clear insights about the extent of realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills which was fairly satisfactory as proven by the total weighted point of 3.24.

Table 4
Roles to Which the School Managers Perform to Enhance Leadership Skills as Perceived by the Teachers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
School Mangers' Role to Enhance Leadership Skills	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weighted Point	Average Weighted Point	Descriptive Equivalent
1. An organizer, skillful in establishing various kinds of programs of values to teachers.	68 272	42 126	18 36	7 7	441	3.27	FS
2. A master teacher, able to demonstrate effective / good teaching.	64 256	42 126	18 36	11 11	429	3.18	FS
3. A strong leader, who knows how to work with groups and get the most of it.	83 332	29 87	18 36	5 5	460	3.41	VS
4. A stimulator, who suggest ideas for teachers to consider.	78 312	31 93	17 34	9 9	448	3.32	FS
5. A coordinator, who seeks to achieve articulation which programs, level and helps teachers become aware of each other's problem.	66 264	46 138	17 34	6 6	442	3.27	FS
6. As orientor, who takes responsibility for helping teachers who are new to the system and community to	74 296	33 99	22 44	6 6	445	3.30	FS

become acquainted.							
7. As consultant, who responds to individual teachers needing his expertise.	70 280	38 114	21 42	6 6	442	3.27	FS
8. A public relation person, who may be involved to interpret the curriculum to the public.	66 264	40 120	20 40	9 9	433	3.21	FS
9. A researcher, who conducts action research.	50 200	45 135	22 44	18 18	397	2.94	FS
10. A change agent, a catalyst for helping teacher to change and improve.	73 272	33 99	19 38	10 10	439	3.25	FS
Total Average Weighted Point						3.24	FS

This implied that the school managers had been doing their roles fairly that there was a need of aspiring for a very satisfactory performance of roles to achieve quality instructions in their own respective schools. These managers seemed to just perform their roles ordinarily and not extra ordinarily. They need to consider their roles as significant factors in improving instruction as they are considered leaders and managers expected to take a lead and manage.

Table 5 presents the extent of realization of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the school managers as perceived by them. Therefore were 30 school managers concerned.

The problems considered in the table were: lack of material time for instructional supervision was described serious with an average weighted point of 2.83; limited finding for in-service activities was rated 2.57 which was described as serious; too many intervening factors / overlapping school activities was describe as fairly serious with an average weighted point of 3.20, negative attitudes towards supervisory assistance was fairly serious with an average weighted point of 2.87; inadequate professional preparation of school officials fairly serious with an average weighted point 2.43; poor library facilities was described fairly serious with an average weighted point of 2.73; inadequate provision of counseling services was serious proven by an average weighted point of 273; inadequate parents assistance was rated 240 described as serious; delayed communication from higher authority described serious as proven by the average weighted point o 2.53; lack of incentives for teachers to conduct innovations was described serious with an average weighted point of 2.33; described as serious, lack of continuity in-service for teachers, serious with an average weighted point of 2.60, and lack of books guides and teacher's manual serious as proven by the average weighted point of 2.43. Looking at the table clearly, it could be note that the extent of realization of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the school manager was really serious as

proven by the total average weighted point of 2.66.

Table 5

Degree of the Seriousness of the Problems that Affect the Instructional Leadership Performance as Perceived by the School Managers

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weight ed Point	Averag e Weight ed Point	Descript ive Equival ent
1. Lack of material for instructional supervision.	8 32	12 36	7 14	3 3	85	2.56	S
2. Limited funding for in-service activities.	10 40	10 30	6 12	4 4	86	2.54	S
3. Too many intervening factors / overlapping school activities.	15 60	8 24	5 10	2 2	96	2.76	FS
4. Negative attitudes towards supervisory assistance.	10 40	10 30	6 12	4 4	86	2.83	FS
5. Inadequate professional preparation of school officials.	6 24	9 27	7 14	8 8	73	3.20	FS
6. Poor study habits of students.	14 56	6 18	8 16	2 2	82	2.87	S
7. Inadequate provision of counseling services.	5 20	6 18	15 30	4 4	72	2.43	S
8. Poor library facilities.	6 24	10 30	8 16	6 6	76	2.73	FS
9. Inadequate parent assistance.	9 36	10 30	9 18	2 2	86	2.40	S
10. Delayed communication from higher authorities.	10 40	10 30	8 16	2 2	88	2.53	FS
11. Lack of incentives for teachers to conduct innovations.	2 8	13 39	8 16	7 7	70	2.87	FS
12. Poor management of time and resources.	4 16	14 42	8 16	4 4	78	2.33	S

13. Lack of continuity in-service for teachers.	6 24	11 33	8 16	5 5	83	2.60	S
14. Lack of specialization for teachers.	6 24	11 33	8 16	5 5	83	2.77	FS
15. Lack of books, guides, and teacher's manual.	5 20	9 27	10 20	6 6	73	2.43	S
Total Average Weighted Point						2.66	FS

This implied that there should be an urgent task of solving the problems especially on intervening factors or overlapping school activities which was serious so that by doing so they could smoothly perform their roles as instructional leaders and improve their performance as well. There should be a cooperative endeavor both governmental organizations and community people to like the seriousness of the problems.

Table 6 presents the 15 factors or problems that affect the instructional leadership performance as perceived by the teachers.

Out of the 15 factors or problems fairly serious like: too many intervening factors/overlapping school activities with an average weighted point of 2.76 (fairly serious); poor study habits of students with an average weighted point of 2.67 (fairly serious); and poor management of time and resources with an average weighted point of 2.64 (fairly serious).

All the other problems were described as serious which were as follows: lack of material time for instructional supervision with an average weighted point of 2.76; limited finding for in-service activities with an average weighted point of 2.54; negative attitudes toward supervisory assistance with an average weighted point of 2.54; poor library facilities with an average weighted point of 2.59; inadequate parent assistance with an average weighted point of 2.44; lack of incentive for teachers to conduct innovations with an average weighted point of 2.58; lack of continuity in – service for teachers with an average weighted point of 2.55. inadequate professional preparation of school officials with an average weighted point of 2.31; and lack of specialization of teachers with an average weighted point of 2.42.

Table 6
Extent of Realization of the Seriousness of the Problems that Affect the Instructional Leadership Performance as Perceived by the teacher

EXTENT OF REALIZATION							
	VS 4	FS 3	S 2	P 1	Total Weight ed Point	Averag e Weight ed Point	Descript ive Equival ent
1. Lack of material for instructional	24 96	45 135	48 196	18 18	345	2.56	S

supervision.							
2. Limited funding for in-service activities.	28 112	36 108	52 104	19 19	343	2.54	S
3. Too many intervening factors / overlapping school activities.	31 123	51 153	43 86	10 10	373	2.76	FS
4. Negative attitudes towards supervisory assistance.	26 104	43 129	44 88	22 22	343	2.54	FS
5. Inadequate professional preparation of school officials.	19 76	32 96	56 112	28 28	321	2.31	S
6. Poor study habits of students.	37 148	34 102	47 94	17 17	361	2.67	FS
7. Inadequate provision of counseling services.	23 97	42 126	47 94	23 23	288	2.13	S
8. Poor library facilities.	26 104	44 132	49 98	16 16	350	2.59	S
9. Inadequate parent assistance.	27 108	38 114	49 98	21 21	341	2.52	S
10. Delayed communication from higher authorities.	25 100	37 111	46 92	27 27	330	2.44	S
11. Lack of incentives for teachers to conduct innovations.	32 128	36 108	46 92	21 21	349	2.58	S
12. Poor management of time and resources.	36 114	38 114	37 76	23 23	357	2.64	FS
13. Lack of continuity in-service for teachers.	24 96	44 132	40 80	27 27	335	2.48	S
14. Lack of specialization for teachers.	22 88	44 132	38 76	31 31	327	2.42	S
15. Lack of books, guides, and teacher's manual.	28 112	44 132	37 74	26 26	344	2.55	S
Total Average Weighted Point						2.34	S

Analyzing the table closely, it could be gleaned that the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the managers as perceived by the teachers were serious

that was proven by the total average weighted point of 2.34.

The school managers found the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance affective and that they disturb their competencies on leadership and management for instruction.

It is implied therefore that these problems should be minimized if not eradicated to ensure the excellent performance of the school managers on instructional leadership from fairly serious to not serious if possible so that excellence can be achieve.

Table 7 presents the comparison between the perceptions of the school managers and teachers of the secondary schools in the first congressional district of Pangasinan on the instructional leadership skills which were: as provider, instructional resources leader, communicator, and visible presence. It had a computed value 0.033 and tabular value of 3.182. The computed value was lesser than the tabular value therefore the null hypothesis was accepted which was no significant difference.

Table 7
Comparison Between the Perception of the School Administrators and Teachers on the Extent to which Instructional Leadership Skills are Manifested by the Secondary School Administrator in the District of Pangasinan

N=30 school managers =135 secondary school teachers						
Instructional Leadership Skills	School Managers TWP X_1	DE	Sec. Sch. Teachers TWP X_2	DE	X_1^2	X_2^2
a. Provider	3.51	VS	3.56	VS	12.32	12.67
b. Instructional Resources Leader	3.16	P	3.25	FS	9.98	10.56
c. Communicator	3.39	FS	3.26	S	11.49	10.63
d. Visible Presence	3.36	S	3.39	S	12.29	11.49

$Df_3=3.182$ $Lo = 0.05$

Results $t_c = 0.033$; $t_b@ 0.05$, $df 3=3.182$

Findings = $t_c < t_b$

Result = No significant difference

Decision = H_0 is accepted

Table 8 presents the comparison between the perception of the school managers and teachers of the secondary schools of the first Congressional District of Pangasinan on the extent of realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership roles. The suggested roles were: as organizer with a total weighted point of 3.43 and 3.27; demonstrate good and effective with a total weighted point of 3.20 and 3.18, a strong leader with a weighted point of 3.53 and 3.41; a stimulator with a weighted point of 3.53 and 3.32, a coordinator with a weighted point of 2.47 and 3.27, as orientor with a weighted point of 3.57 and 3.30, as consultant

with a weighted point of 3.53 and 3.27; as public relation person with a weighted point of 3.47 and 3.21, as researcher with a weighted point of 2.90 and 2.94; and a change agent with a weighted point of 3.13 and 3.25.

The computed value of A was 727 and the tabular value was 2.262 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 level of significance. The computed value of A was lesser than the tabular value of A was no significant difference. Therefore the decision of the null hypotheses was accepted.

Table 8
Comparison Between the Perception of the Secondary School Heads and Teachers on the Extent of Realization to which the School Managers Perform the Roles to Enhance Leadership Skills as Perceived by the teachers

	School Managers TWP X ₁	DE	Sec. Sch. Teachers TWP X ₂	DE	X ₁ ²	X ₂ ²
1. An organizer, skillful in establishing various kinds of programs of values to teachers.	3.43	VS	3.27	FS	11.76	10.69
2. Demonstrate effective good teaching.	3.20	S	3.18	FS	10.24	10.11
3. A strong leader	3.53	VS	3.32	VS	12.46	11.63
4. A stimulator	3.53	VS	3.27	VS	12.46	10.02
5. A coordinator	2.47	P	3.30	FS	6.10	10.69
6. As orientor	3.57	VS	3.27	VS	12.74	10.89
7. As consultant	3.53	VS	3.21	FS	12.46	10.69
8. A public relation person	3.47	VS	3.21	FS	12.04	10.30
9. A researcher	2.90	P	2.94	P	8.41	8.64
10. A change agent	3.13	S	3.25	FS	2.80	10.56

Df 9 = 2.262 Lo = 0.05

Results tc = .727; tb@ 0.05, dfa = 2.262

Findings = tc < tb

Result = No significant difference

Decision = H₀ is accepted

Table 9 presents the comparison between the perception of the school managers and teachers of the secondary schools of the first congressional district of Pangasinan on the extent of realization of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the said school managers.

Table 9
Comparison Between the Perception of the Secondary School Administrators and Teachers
of the Malasiqui District II-A on the Extent of Realization of the Seriousness of the
Problems that Affect the Instructional
Leadership Performance

Extent of realization of the seriousness of the problem	School Managers TWP X_1	DE	Sec. Sch. Teachers TWP X_2	X_1^2	X_2^2
1. Lack of material for instructional supervision.	2.83	FS	2.56	8.00	6.55
2. Limited funding for in-service activities.	2.87	FS	2.54	8.24	6.45
3. Too many intervening factors / overlapping school activities.	3.20	VS	2.76	10.24	7.62
4. Negative attitudes towards supervisory assistance.	2.87	FS	2.54	8.24	6.45
5. Inadequate professional preparation of school officials.	2.43	NS	2.31	5.90	5.34
6. Poor study habits of students.	2.73	S	2.67	7.45	7.1
7. Inadequate provision of counseling services.	2.40	NS	2.13	5.76	4.54
8. Poor library facilities.	2.53	NS	2.59	6.40	6.71
9. Inadequate parent assistance.	2.87	FS	2.52	8.24	6.35
10. Delayed communication from higher authorities.	2.93	FS	2.44	8.58	5.95
11. Lack of incentives for teachers to conduct innovations.	2.33	NS	2.58	5.43	6.66
12. Poor management of time and resources.	2.60	S	2.64	6.76	6.97
13. Lack of continuity in-service for teachers.	2.77	FS	2.48	7.67	6.15
14. Lack of specialization for teachers.	2.77	FS	2.42	7.67	5.86
15. Lack of books, guides,	2.43	NS	2.55	5.90	6.50

and teacher's manual.					
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tb@0.05 level of significance

df 14 = 2.145

Findings = $t_l < t_b$

Decision = H_0 is accepted

Result = No significant difference

These were: lack of material with a total weighted point of 2.83 and 2.56; limited funding with a total weighted point of 2.87 and 2.54; too many intervening factors with a total weighted point of 3.20 and 2.76; negative attitude with a total weighted point of 2.87 and 2.54; inadequate professional preparation with a total weighted point of 2.43 and 2.31; poor study habits with a total weighted point of 2.73 and 2.67; inadequate provision of counseling services with a total weighted point of 2.40 and 2.13; poor library facilities with a total weighted point of 2.53 and 2.59; inadequate parents assistance with a average weighted point of 2.87 and 2.52; delayed communication with an average weighted point of 2.93 and 2.44; lack of incentives with an average weighted point of 2.33 and 2.58; poor management of time with an average weighted point 2.60 and 2.64; lack of continuity with an average weighted point 2.77 and 2.48, lack of specialization with an average weighted point 2.77 and 2.42, and lack of books with an average weighted point of 2.43 and 2.55.

The computed value of A was 2.93 and the tabular value of 14 at 0.05 level of significance. The computed value of A was greater than the tabular value of A which significant. Therefore, the decision of the null hypothesis was rejected.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter of the research presents the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations from the research for action.

The study dealt with the “Instructional Leadership Skills of the Secondary School Managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan for the school year 2025 – 2026.

1. What is the extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the secondary school managers as: a. provide b. instructional resources leader c. communicator d. visible presence.
2. Is there any significant difference between the perceptions of the teacher respondents and the school managers as to the extent to which the instructional leadership skills are manifested by the school managers: a. provider b. instructional resources leader c. communicator d. visible presence?
3. What is the extent to which the secondary difference between the perception of the secondary school teacher respondents and the secondary school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills?
4. What is the degree of seriousness of the problems affect the instructional leadership performance of the secondary school managers of First Congressional District of Pangasinan?
5. Is there any significant difference between the perception of the secondary school teachers and the secondary school managers on the degree of seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance of the secondary school managers of Pangasinan I?

Salient Findings

A. Personal Profile

1. The highest percentage of the respondents from the school managers belong to the age bracket of 46-50 as revealed by 27 or 8 as a total points.
2. There were more female secondary school managers whose age bracket belonged to 46 – 50 than the males.

B. Civil Status of the respondents

1. Most of the secondary school managers were married as revealed by the total percentage of 56.66.

C. Designated positions of the school managers

1. Most of the secondary school managers had a designation of Principal I as projected by the total point of 12 or 40 percents.
2. The least was the position of the Department Head as revealed by revealed by 2 or 6.67 percents.

D. Professional profile of the Secondary School Manager respondents in terms of educational qualification

1. Most of the school managers completed their academic requirements in MA as revealed in the table with a total percentage of 37.
2. There were no among the school managers who finished their Ed.D. or Ph.D. degree as revealed in the table with zero point or percentage.

E. Number of years as Secondary School Managers

1. Most of the secondary school managers had experience of 10 to 15 years as revealed by the total percentage of 60.
2. There were no school managers who had experience of 26 years and above as revealed by the zero percents in the table.

F. Relevant in-service-training by the Secondary School Managers

1. Most of the secondary school managers attended regional in-service-training as revealed by the total percentage of 50.
2. Most of the secondary school teacher respondents attended divisions level in-service-training as proven by the total points of 60 or 45 percent.

G. Professional materials being read by the Secondary School Managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan

1. The greatest number of school manager respondents read newspaper or periodical revealed by the 14 or 47 percent.

H. Extent of realization of the leadership skills as provider as perceived by the secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan.

H.a. As Provider

1. The secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan are in evaluating the effectiveness of change revealed by the average weighted point of 3.07.
2. Generally, the secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan had very satisfactory leadership skill as provider revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.51 which was very satisfactory.

H.b. As Instructional Resources Leader

1. Generally, the secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan were poor in instructional resources leadership skills as manifested by the total average weighted point of 3.16 described as poor.

H.c. Leadership Skill as Communicator

1. The secondary school managers were fairly satisfactory in their leadership skills as communicator revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.39 described as fairly satisfactory.

H.d. Leadership Skills Visible Presence

1. The secondary school managers were only satisfactory in their rating on the leadership skills as visible revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.36.

I. Extent of realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skills as perceived by them and the teachers.

1. The school managers perform their roles to enhance their leadership skill very satisfactory as revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.38.

J. Extent of realization of the seriousness of the problem that affect instructional leadership performance as perceived by them and the teachers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan

1. Too many intervening and overlapping school activities is very serious problem as revealed by the 3.20 average weighted point.
2. Generally, the problem that affect the instructional leadership performance as perceived by the secondary school managers were serious as revealed by the total average weighted

point of 2.70.

Conclusions

After a thorough analysis of the findings from the research, the following conclusions were drawn:

A. Personal Attributes

1. The greatest number of school managers as revealed by the table fell within the range of forty one to fifty five which could mean, they have enough maturity and experience to perform their job.
2. Most of the secondary school managers were married which might affect their leadership roles for they had greater responsibilities to attend to in both home and school.

B. Instructional Leadership Skills

1. The extent of realization of the leadership skill as provider as perceived by the secondary school managers was very satisfactory although there was one aspect that was poor and this was on evaluating the effectiveness of change.
2. The extent of realization of the leadership skills as instructional resources leader as perceived by the school managers was poor as revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.16.
3. The extent of realization of the leadership skills as communicator as perceived by the school managers was fairly satisfactory as revealed by the total average weighted point of 3.39.
4. The extent of realization of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance as perceived by the school managers was serious as revealed by the total average weighted point of 2.70.
5. The extent of realization of the leadership skills of the secondary school managers as provider as perceived by the teachers was very satisfactory with a total average weighted point of 3.56.
6. The extent of realization of the leadership skills of the school manager as instructional resources leader as perceived by the teachers was fairly satisfactory as projected by the total average weighted point of 3.25.
7. The extent of realization of the leadership skills of the school manager as communicator as perceived by the teachers manifested by the total average weighted point of 3.26.
8. The extent of realization of the leadership skills of the school managers as visible presence perceived by the total teacher was satisfactory as proven by the total average weighted point of 3.39.

C. School Heads performance of roles

1. The extent of realization to which the school managers perform their roles to enhance leadership skill as perceived by the teachers was fairly satisfactory with a total average weighted point of 3.24.
2. The extent of realization of the seriousness of the problems that affect the instructional leadership performance as perceived by the teachers was fairly serious as revealed by the total average weighted point of 2.52.

Recommendations

After a logical analysis, interpretation of salient findings and conclusions were done, the following significant recommendations were highly formulated:

1. The secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan should aspire to earn experience, qualification and training's especially in leadership skills as early as 30 years of age so that they could make use of their ideals and youthful energy and enthusiasm and that they could be promoted to higher position from Principal I to II, III or IV and not just Principal I, Head Teacher of Officer-in-Charge if chances and opportunities be given.
2. The secondary school managers of the First Congressional District of Pangasinan should purpose their studies up to doctoral degree education to upgrade qualitatively their competence and skills for instruction and leadership.
3. The secondary school managers should avail of the long term national if not international scholarship grants, and avail of the national innovative kind of seminar training if necessary and if opportunities warrant to keep themselves abreast in leadership skills and instruction.
4. The secondary school managers should not only read magazines or periodicals but also quality books and materials for research, to enhance their diversified leadership skills.
5. The secondary school managers should upgrade the factors on evaluating the effectiveness of change on the aspect of leadership skills as provider.
6. The secondary school managers should aspire to improve their instructional resources leadership skills from poor to very satisfactory so that effective change and good school atmosphere cold happen by thorough and actual preparation in school and community activities.
7. The school managers should work on the improvement of their skills as communicator from fairly satisfactory to very satisfactory by constant reading, writing, and speaking engagement activities.
8. The secondary school managers should do something to very satisfactory dispense their leadership skills on visible presence and not just satisfactorily do it.
9. The should minimize too many intervening and overlapping school activities since those affect too much instructions. They should do something to solve the seriousness of the problems that affect instructional leadership performance.
10. Similar studies should be conducted in other divisions of the region and consider the adoption of the suggested action plan of this research.

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